

THE EVALUATION OF STUDENT TEACHERS ABILITY TO USE DIFFERENT TEACHING METHODS DURING TEACHING PRACTICE: AN APPRAISAL FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF COOPERATING TEACHERS

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Abstract:

Teacher education is the bedrock of the quality of the educational system of every country. For this quality to be realized, it is important to constantly monitor the stages (theoretical, teaching practice, research project) involved in teacher education. This paper sought to evaluate student teacher's ability to use different teaching methods during teaching practice: an appraisal from the perspective of cooperating teachers. The survey research designed was employed to get the opinions of 194 cooperating teachers selected through the simple random sampling technique. The subjects completed a self-response questionnaire made up of closed-ended items. Data analysis was done using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences to obtain frequencies, simple percentages, mean scores, and standard deviations were used. The results obtained revealed that participants were divided in their opinions in the research objective that guided the study.

Keywords: evaluation, student teachers, ability, teaching methods, teaching practice, appraisal, perspective, cooperating teachers

1. Introduction

In all countries and educational systems, teaching practice is an integral part of the initial training of teachers. Many schools have been created, by missionaries, the government, and private partners to train teachers for various levels of education in Cameroon. The University of Buea was created as a consequence of the Higher Education Reforms of 1993. The Faculty of Education is one of its establishments with the following as mission:

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to prepare educational personnel in order to promote excellence at all levels of schooling, as well as undertake professional training and advanced studies in educational sciences. In addition, it is supposed to conduct and develop appropriate research and carry out outreach activities in line with the three traditional missions of a university — teaching, research and outreach.

To achieve this mission, the departments of Educational Foundations and Administration, Educational Psychology and Curriculum Studies and Teaching were created. The department of Curriculum Studies and Teaching (CST) outlined the following specific objectives in its brochure: train development-oriented teachers of quality for secondary grammar schools, teacher training institutions and higher levels of schooling; promote pedagogic excellence at the secondary school level, and carry out outreach activities to improve the teaching and learning process. At the end of the training exercise, it is expected that the student teachers would have had appropriate competences in the dimensions of knowledge, skills and professional attitudes.

Each of the departments of the faculty has a training model that has three main components: coursework, teaching practice or internship and research project. The aim of this study is to evaluate student teacher's ability to use different teaching methods during teaching practice: an appraisal from the perspective of cooperating teachers.

2. Background

Cognizant of an increasing demand for enrolment into primary and secondary education in Cameroon, and the recognition by the government that teachers are critical to the quality of the educational system and its graduates, all efforts needed to guarantee this quality are very indispensable especially in the teacher training process.

The importance the government attaches to education is contained in the formal purpose and specific objectives of Basic, Secondary and Teacher education in Cameroon. The mission, purpose and objectives of Basic, Secondary and Teacher education in Cameroon are laid down in the Law of orientation of Basic, Secondary and Teacher Education in Cameroon (Law No. 98/004 of 14 April, 1998).

According to Section 4 of this law, the general purpose of education shall be to train children for their intellectual, physical, civic and moral development and their smooth integration into the society bearing in mind prevailing economic, socio-cultural, political and moral factors. Section 37:1 of this law describes teachers as principal guarantors of quality education.

In this respect, teachers are entitled, within the limit of the means available to suitable living conditions, as well as to appropriate initial and continuing training. Also, Section 39 of the law states that teachers shall be bound to teach, educate, provide educational guidance, promote the quest for scientific knowledge, carry out assessment and be of moral rectitude; they shall abide by the instruments in force, in particular, the internal regulations of the establishment where they teach.

With such an expectation in mind, teacher trainers must engage student teachers to become reflective practitioners during and after the teacher training process. The teaching practice component of the teacher training programme is indispensable especially as it gives student teachers the opportunity to put theory into practice.

According to Bell and Gilbert (1996), a lot of questions persist with respect to how much influence teaching practice plays in the student teacher's acquisition of knowledge necessary for effective teaching and the learning process. This study assumes that, if well conceptualized and implemented, teaching practice can make a substantial contribution to the pre-service education of the would-be teachers.

Berstein (2000) defined that teaching practice is the art and science of organizing knowledge and demonstrating relevant skills. It is the formal practical training of the would-be teachers. The purpose is to enable them to apply competencies (knowledge, skills, and professional attitudes) acquired through coursework within teacher training institutions to actual classroom situation. The teaching practice exercise requires student teachers to carry out teaching or related activities under the guidance of cooperating teachers, cooperating school administrators, as well as experts from the teacher training institution for a given period of time. The effectiveness of the exercise depends on how well the student teachers perform clearly identified and stated tasks.

Teaching practice is important as it is intended to equip the would-be teachers with what it takes to be effective in a real-life situation. Anja (2006) asserts that there are constant changes in educational practices as a consequence of environmental changes such as developments in science and instructional technology.

These changes present challenges that teacher trainers and trainees must face. If teachers are described as the principal guarantors of quality education (Law no. 98/004), then they must be assisted to be reflective and effective practitioners. Teaching practice is therefore a key component in most teacher education programs in general and that of the University of Buea, in particular. At the University of Buea, teaching practice is structured in two phases a first phase during the second year of studies (CST 306 Teaching Practice I) and the second during the third (final) year (CST 404 Teaching Practice II).

Anja (2006) proposed the following general objectives of teaching practice:

- 1) to smoothen the transition from the role model of student-teacher to that of the professional in the field.
- 2) to give the student teacher an opportunity to put in to practice the ideas, skills and attitudes learnt theoretically in the classroom in order to become competent.
- 3) to develop student teachers' professional attitude/growth toward the teaching profession.
- 4) to improve on student teachers' mastery of the subject matter in which they are or to teach.
- 5) to help the training college assess the worth of her student teachers before graduation.

- 6) to enable the trainee to apply the general principles of teaching in a real-life situation.
- 7) to develop student teachers' skills in classroom management.
- 8) to give student teachers the opportunity to apply the methods of teaching in a classroom sitting.
- 9) to improve on student teachers understanding of the stages of child development.
- 10) to help trainers develop skills in the use of instructional materials, to communicate with learners for effective learning.
- 11) to enable students, identify the purposes, the programme and the administrative organization of the school system.
- 12) to lead student-teachers to be resourceful and creative in planning, developing and in evaluating experiences.

It is worth noting that methods of teaching will vary by teacher, content of instruction and other variables. For greater effectiveness and efficiency, the education and training of teachers need to provide them with a body of professional knowledge that undergirds both knowledge of general pedagogic principles and skills including knowledge of subject matter.

Furthermore, Tchombe (2004) asserts that teaching methods can be general or specific. General or generic teaching methods are methods that can be used to teach more than one subject while specific teaching methods are methods that can be used to teach specific subjects. For instance, there are certain methods or procedures that are used in the teaching of mathematics that may not be appropriate in the teaching of Chemistry.

Tambo (2012) reinforces this perspective and in addition identifies some generic methods.

A. Explicit Teaching Method

Rosenshine (1987), cited in Tambo (2012), asserts that explicit teaching has to do with a step by step delivery of a lesson with active participation of all the students. It is also called direct teaching. In this method, the teacher presents content in steps to give the students time to assimilate them. The teacher also constantly checks students understanding and gives exercises for students to do under his/her guidance. This method is good in teaching specific skills and most applicable in the teaching of mathematical concepts and procedures, grammar, scientific concepts, and other procedural knowledge. To use this method effectively, a teacher is expected to start a lesson by reviewing previous lessons, present new materials and in the course of this gives learners tasks under close guidance and supervision. The teacher should also inform the learner of his/her performance.

B. Recitation Method

Tambo (2012) asserts that when a teacher teaches learners by calling on them to answer questions, to read in turn or to give answers to homework and other assignments, it is called recitation. Stodolosky, Ferguson and Wimpelberg (1981:123), cited in Tambo

(2012), say that recitation usually involves relatively short exchanges between students and teachers and preferred when a teacher wants to introduce a lesson, review a lesson, to check whether students have understood instructions etc.

C. Drill and Practice Method

Tambo (2012) asserts drill is an intensive repetition to ensure quick and accurate responses. The intention is to establish associations. A combination of drill and practice leads to automatic remembering of certain mental associations. Practice has to do with learners acquiring the ability to do something. A teacher may drill learners on spelling and tenses but practice requires that learners write essays or letters using the correct spelling and tenses. Student teachers on internship can use this method to help learners' master information that is a prerequisite to other learning activities.

D. The Pure Lecture Method

According to Tambo (2012), this method involves a teacher presenting subject matter or information to a group of audience or learners. It is typically used in the university level of education. This method does not give learners the opportunity to ask questions during lectures. Learners are always passive in class. But this method is very economical because it is less time consuming as much amount of work can be covered within a shorter period of time. However, it tends to make students more passive and teacher dependent. Teachers need to understand how to use this alongside with other methods to enhance understanding.

E. The Lecture-Demonstration Method

This approach is a combination of lecture and demonstration. Demonstration is when a teacher does something in the presence of the learners to show how this thing is done. When a lecture is combined with demonstration, teaching is likely to become more effective because the teacher takes up some time to explain to the learners the issue/topic under study. When using this method teachers have to lecture, demonstrate and thus test the learners. This is to ensure that the learners should be able to demonstrate the topic or lesson under study.

F. The Illustrated Lecture Method

When pictures, charts, diagrams, film slides and other teaching materials are used to illustrate or explain relationships or facts, principles and ideas, it is called the illustrated lecture method. This method does not deal with concrete materials, but rather with illustrations or is mainly in graphics. This method is good in teaching principles like Geography.

G. The Laboratory Method

According to Tambo (2012), this method has to do with learners working under the guidance of a teacher to investigate some aspects of a topic. Through this method,

learners learn how to handle tools, appliances, materials and analyze data or facts and concepts more objectively and concretely. This approach, developed in the physical and life sciences, is a teaching and learning process that uses experimentation to discover and verify physical laws and principles as well as other forms of relationships. Today it is widely used in all areas of the curriculum.

H. The Dramatization and Role Play Method

Dramatization is when learners try to make a life situation, issue or problem clear to themselves and to the audience by playing the roles of real or imaginary people related to that issue, problem or situation. This is usually based on prepared scripts which are rehearsed and memorized. In a situation where dramatization is done without scripts, memorization or rehearsal, it is called role play. This approach is suitable in subjects like History, Literature, Civics and related subjects. For the role playing to be effective, at least three conditions should be fulfilled: a) the issue should be clear in the minds of the learners, b) the class should have a common interest or group feeling on the issue, and c) the role playing should be seen by the class as a means of learning.

The teacher should guide this to ensure that the intended knowledge is achieved.

I. The Cooperative Learning Method

Clark, Wideman, and Eadie (1990), cited in Tambo (2012), assert that cooperative learning is said to occur when learners work in small mixed ability learning teams. This approach gives learners the opportunity to interact with each other, learn from the teacher and also learn from the world around them. These groups need not be extremely large (about 5 is okay). This number will also depend on the task to be accomplished. When teachers use this method, they should check that all members of the group contribute in the work.

J. The Discussion Method

Arends (1997 p. 285) asserts that discussing teaching method involves verbal exchange of ideas among the students and the teachers. The main purpose of this teaching method is to help students improve on their thinking and communication skills and to promote their involvement in the lesson, encourage tolerance for the views of others, as well as fairness and open mindedness. This method can be used in teaching all subjects of the curriculum. It is perhaps the most dynamic method of teaching. Teachers are expected to master the techniques involved in this method and make sure that all students participate (Tambo, 2000).

It is worth noting that a combination of these teaching methods will make an effective classroom.

3. Theoretical Framework

The system and self-efficacy theories are considered relevant in this study.

3.1 The System Theory

The system theory was developed by Ludwig von Bertalanffy (1956). It was developed as a reaction to piecemeal approaches of studying organizations, phenomenon and solving problems. According to the theory the analysis of an organization or attempts to solve problems can be approached from a systemic perspective. A system is made up of parts that are interrelated. Each part has certain functions to perform in order to ensure that the whole is maintained at desired levels.

This theory is considered relevant to this study because the training of would-be teachers in the Faculty of Education requires many components and many actors. For example, the training of teachers has been broken down into coursework, teaching practice and a research project. Only students who perform well in all three components are considered to have met graduation requirements. Each component or actor has an important contribution to make to ensure the effectiveness of training. Against this backdrop, teaching practice and cooperating teachers constitute important components whose effectiveness is critical to the ability of the Faculty to achieve stated objectives of teacher training.

3.2 Self-efficacy Theory

Generally, the aim of teacher education before and during service is to ensure that they are more effective. In other words, good training increases the ability of an individual to carryout assigned tasks in order to achieve desired objectives. Bandura used the concept of efficacy to refer to perceptions of ability by individuals charged with certain responsibilities. Individuals can either perceive that they have the relevant training to do what is expected of them or they can feel that they do not. Teachers who feel that they can teach and make a difference in the lives of all children can be described as having a sense of high efficacy. Such teachers are not likely to give up when they face difficulties and will be the case with teachers who doubt their efficacy vis-à-vis assigned responsibilities. A high sense of teacher efficacy has been associated with higher levels of teacher motivation, commitment and productivity as well as higher levels of student achievement of desired outcomes. The quality of training is related to perceptions of efficacy among teachers.

4. Statement of the Problem

The preparation of quality teachers should be a key concern of all teacher training institutions in general and the Faculty of Education in the University of Buea in particular. This is because the quality of teachers is critical to efforts to create and sustain productive teaching and learning environment. This has been recognized by the government of Cameroon in Law 98/004 of April 14, 1998. Teachers are described in this law as guarantors of quality education. The practical training in schools gives “would-be teachers” first-hand experience as to what would be required of them in the real world of practice upon graduation. If teachers are expected to perform well in real world

situations, then their performance during teaching practice has to be closely monitored and evaluated in order to determine strengths and weaknesses in order to inform policy and practice. The problem that has provoked this study is that this is not regularly done. At the end of each teaching practice session, the views of all stakeholders involved in the process need to be known. Only after this knowledge can more informed actions be taken to improve the education of teachers in general and the improvement of the teaching practice component in particular. Strengthening links with schools and institutions used for the practical training of students is one of the objectives of the Faculty of Education.

4.1 Objective of the Study

To investigate perceptions of the ability of student teachers to use different teaching methods.

4.2 Research Question

Do student teachers demonstrate effective use of the different teaching methods?

5. Methodology

5.1 Research Design

The survey research design is used in this study. Surveys inquire about the feelings, preferences, motivations, attitudes, accomplishments and experiences of a group of people or individuals (Amin, 2005). The survey research design requires data to be collected from subjects using questionnaire or interview guide. This study collected needed data using a questionnaire, designed for cooperating teachers.

Table 1: Cooperating Schools

S/N	Names of Schools
1	Bilingual Grammar School Molyko
2	Government Bilingual High School Muea
3	Government High School Bokova
4	Government High School Bokwango
5	Government Secondary School Bolifamba – Mile 16
6	Government Secondary School Bomaka
7	Government Secondary School Buea Town
8	Government Secondary School Great Soppo
9	Government Secondary School Tole
10	Government Secondary School Wokeka
11	Baptist High School Buea
12	Jules Peter’s Memorial College Bokwango
13	Presbyterian Comprehensive Secondary School Buea Town
14	St. Joseph’s College Sasse
15	Our Lady of Mount Camel Muea

Source: Department of CST, University of Buea.

5.2 Population of the Study

According to statistics from the Department of Curriculum Studies and Teaching of the Faculty of Education – University of Buea, teaching practice exercise is conducted in 15 secondary schools in Buea Sub-Division. The table present cooperating schools used for the teaching practice exercise.

Also, according to the statistics from the Regional Delegation of Secondary Education for the South West Region, there are 782 teachers in all the Secondary Schools in Buea Sub-division where University of Buea student-teachers carry out teaching practice.

Table 1.1 below presents the number of teachers per school where teaching practice is done.

Table 1.1: The distribution of teachers per cooperating school

S/N	Names of Schools	No. of Teachers
1	Bilingual Grammar School Molyko	174
2	Government Bilingual High School Muea	106
3	Government High School Bokova	33
4	Government High School Bokwango	104
5	Government Secondary School Bolifamba – Mile 16	19
6	Government Secondary School Bomaka	27
7	Government Secondary School Buea Town	37
8	Government Secondary School Great Soppo	22
9	Government Secondary School Tole	29
10	Government Secondary School Wokeka	1
11	Baptist High School Buea	39
12	Jules Peter’s Memorial College Bokwango	15
13	Presbyterian Comprehensive Secondary School Buea Town	62
14	St. Joseph’s College Sasse	62
15	Our Lady of Mount Camel Muea	52
	Total	782

Source: Adapted from the statistics of the Regional Delegation of Secondary Education for the South West Region (2010).

Since each teacher in the cooperating schools is likely to be a cooperating teacher in his or her own field of teaching, the population of the study therefore was approximately 782 teachers of geography.

5.4 Sample and Sampling Technique

Out of a population of 782 cooperating teachers, 200 or 25.6 % were selected for the study. Two sampling techniques - purposive sampling was used to select the schools and simple random sampling to select cooperating teachers. Only teachers in schools in which student-teachers carry out teaching practice were involved in the study. The sample of teachers was selected by using the simple random sampling technique. Table 1.2 below reveals the population and sample selected from each of the schools.

Table 1.2: Population and sample from each school

S/N	Names of Schools	Population of Teachers	Sample
1	Bilingual Grammar School Molyko	174	45
2	Government Bilingual High School Muea	106	27
3	Government High School Bokova	33	8
4	Government High School Bokwango	104	27
5	Government Secondary School Bolifamba	19	5
6	Government Secondary School Bomaka	27	7
7	Government Secondary School Buea Town	37	9
8	Government Secondary School Great Soppo	22	6
9	Government Secondary School Tole	1	7
10	Government Secondary School Wokeka	29	0
11	Baptist High School Buea	39	10
12	Jules Peter's Memorial College Bokwango	15	4
13	Presbyterian Comprehensive Secondary School Buea Town	62	16
14	St. Joseph's College Sasse	62	16
15	Our Lady of Mount Camel Muea	52	13
	Total	782	200

5.5 Instrumentation and Data Analyses

Data collection for this study was done using a questionnaire made up of nine (9) closed-ended questionnaire items. Items for the questionnaire were derived from the review of related literature. Data analysis was done using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 24 for windows to obtain descriptive statistics (more especially, frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviations). Bar charts have been used to enhance the visual appreciation of the findings (Background information of respondents). A total of 200 copies of the questionnaire were distributed and 194 copies were completed and returned to the investigator giving a return rate of 97%.

6. Presentation of Findings and Discussion

Nine (9) closed-ended questionnaire items were designed to answer the research question. Cooperating teachers who participated in the study were provided with 6 grading options with each given a numerical value as follows: Excellent=5, Very Good=4, Good=3, Fair=2.5, Poor=2 and Very Poor=1. Respondents were required to underline what in their opinion, was the most appropriate response option. The mean score for the grades in each item were computed and used to determine whether student teachers make effective use of the different teaching methods. A mean score from 3.00 and above indicates the effective use of the teaching method described while that below 3.00 indicates an ineffective use of the method. Data analysis for all items set to answer the research question is done below using frequencies, percentages, mean scores and standard deviation.

Table 1.4: Frequency of responses to the items aimed at answering research question

Statement	Exc.	V.G.	G.	F.	P.	V.P.	Sample size
Deliver lessons step by step with active participation of all students	0	23	124	3	32	12	194
Ensures relatively short exchange between his/herself and the students during lessons	9	89	93	3	0	0	194
Help students to master vital information by asking them to repeat it two or more times	38	90	29	8	29	0	194
Takes time to lecture and explain new concepts to students who are expected to listen keenly	0	25	114	11	44	0	194
Does explain and at the same time perform the activity in front of students for better understanding	10	35	71	12	66	0	194
Uses charts, pictures and diagrams to explain relationship among variables, facts, principles or ideas	0	0	47	12	124	10	194
Have students make situations, issues or problems clear to themselves by performing the role of imaginary people	0	24	126	3	29	12	194
Have students perform some tasks in mixed ability small groups	9	94	88	3	0	0	194
Engage students in verbal exchange of ideas between them and his/herself	40	85	32	6	31	0	194
G. = Good	F. = Fair	P. = Poor	V.P. =				

Table 1.4 above shows the distribution of the responses by each of the response options. In Table 1.5 that follows the „excellent“, „very good“ and „good“ response options are combined and termed acceptable levels while the „fair“, „poor“ and „very poor“ options are also combined into unacceptable responses. Further combinations under the two broad categories include the „very good“ and „good“ responses and the „poor“ and „very poor“ options.

Data analysis presented in Table 1.5 below shows that the frequency of acceptable level of responses for all the items ranges from 47 (24.25%) to 191 (98.45%). Some of the most acceptable items include student teachers' behaviours to have students perform some tasks in mixed ability small groups (freq.=191 or 98.45%), ensures relatively short exchange between themselves and the students during lessons (freq.=191 or 98.45%), and engage students in verbal exchange of ideas between themselves (freq.=157 or 80.93%). Unacceptable level of responses on the contrary have frequencies ranging from 3 to 146 with the most unacceptable item being that with the opinion that student teachers uses charts, pictures and diagrams to explain relationship among variables, facts, principles or ideas (freq.=146 or 75.26%), followed by the opinion that student teachers does explain

and at the same time perform the activity in front of students for better understanding (freq.=78 or 40.21%).

Table 1.5: Presentation of responses in acceptable and unacceptable levels for all items set to answer research question

Statement	Acceptable level		Unacceptable level		Sample size
	Exc.	V.G./G	F.	P./V. P.	
Deliver lessons step by step with active participation of all students	0	147	3	44	194
Ensures relatively short exchange between his/herself and the students during lessons	9	182	3	0	194
Help students to master vital information by asking them to repeat it two or more times	38	119	8	29	194
Takes time to lecture and explain new concepts to students who are expected to listen keenly	0	139	11	44	194
Does explain and at the same time perform the activity in front of students for better understanding	10	106	12	66	194
Uses charts, pictures and diagrams to explain relationship among variables, facts, principles or ideas	0	47	12	134	194
Have students make situations, issues or problems clear to themselves by performing the role of imaginary people	0	150	3	41	194
Have students perform some tasks in mixed ability small groups	9	182	3	0	194
Engage students in verbal exchange of ideas between them and his/herself	40	117	6	31	194

Table 1.6 present means scores ranging from 2.8 – 3.69, with four of the nine opinion statements having mean scores above the cut-off point of 3.00 and five having mean scores below. This implies that the subjects were divided in their responses as to whether student teachers make effective use of the different teaching methods.

Table 1.6: The means and standard deviations (SD) for all questionnaire items

No.	Statement of teaching activity	Mean	SD
1.	Help students to master vital information by asking them to repeat it two or more times.	3.69	0.96
2.	Engage students in verbal exchange of ideas between them and his/herself.	3.68	0.99
3.	Have students perform some tasks in mixed ability small groups.	3.57	0.59
4.	Ensures relatively short exchange between his/herself and the students during lessons.	3.54	0.59
5.	Does explain and at the same time perform the activity in front of students for better understanding.	2.91	2.22
6.	Takes time to lecture and explain new concepts to students who are expected to listen keenly.	2.87	0.60
7.	Deliver lessons step by step with active participation of all students.	2.82	0.7
8.	Uses charts, pictures and diagrams to explain relationship among variables, facts, principles or ideas.	2.22	0.51
9.	Have students make situations, issues or problems clear to themselves by performing the role of imaginary people.	2.8	0.74

The teaching methods likely used by student teachers during teaching practice according to data analysis include the recitation methods, the discussion method, and cooperative learning method. The unlikely used teaching methods include the lecture demonstration method, the pure lecture method, the explicit teaching method, the illustrated lecture method, and the role play and dramatization method.

Using only a particular or some methods of teaching away from others by a student teacher is not as crediting as using a variety or all the methods because of the diversity among learners.

Some learners are kinaesthetic, others are visual and yet some auditory. According to Tambo (2012) teachers should have in mind that learners do differ in terms of intelligence, skills, habits, emotions, experiences, interests, life goals, adjustments and readiness. Student teachers are supposed to be diverse in their use of teaching methods during teaching practice as such diversity would likely cater for the needs of various characteristics of learners. This is supported by Piaget and Vygotsky's Theories on Constructivism cited in Santrock (2004:50) which states that students construct knowledge through social interaction with others and so encourage a variety of teaching methods including the discussion method, cooperative learning method, the recitation method, the laboratory method, the dramatization and role play method, and the field method; that enable students to explore the world around them and discover or construct new ideas.

Besides, ability to use different teaching methods in more recent times has been found to make a great difference in student learning (Good and Brophy, 2006). However, methods of teaching vary as the original instinctive capacities of individual teachers vary and as past experiences and references also vary (Tchombe, 2004). While the respondents are divided in their opinions as to whether student teachers are able to use different teaching methods, and while more literature holds that it is advantageous to use different teaching methods, the use of variety of methods by student teachers during teaching practice need to be emphasized by the Faculty of Education, and more especially by cooperating teachers.

7. Conclusion

The Faculty of Education over the years has been committing time and resources to train quality teachers through programs encompassing course work and teaching practice. This study has empirically investigated the perceptions of cooperating teachers concerning the effectiveness of teaching practice in the domain of student teachers use of different teaching methods. Data analysis for the research question set to guide the study revealed that cooperating teachers are divided in their opinion as to whether teaching practice is effective thus inconclusive results, although much efforts has been made, improving the quality of teacher training in the University of Buea constitutes an important challenge to the Faculty of Education, the cooperating schools involved and the student teachers themselves; in a framework of shared commitment.

7.1 Implication to Curriculum Studies

Curriculum implementation is a very important phase in the entire curriculum making process. Teachers are charge with a major responsibility to ensure effectiveness in this process. From the findings above, curriculum trainers should be able to encourage diversity in the use of teaching methods. Some subjects are better taught with some particular methods. As such, a sense of varying methods in the teaching and learning process will make lessons learnable and enhance learners inclusiveness.

Curriculum experts must understand that some teachers stick to particular methods and care less whether learning is taking place or not. If such continue, then the major goals of curriculum implementation are thus defeated and making it impossible to realize stated educational goals.

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